

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF THE WORDS RELATED TO FASHION IN ENGLISH
AND UZBEK

Gulnorakhon Tadjimatova

teacher of Andizhan state university

Interfaculty of foreign languages

(exact and natural sciences)

E-mail: gulya.ikramova@mail.ru

Abstract: *in the given article the author tried to show the linguistic features of different words related to fashion and mainly types of clothes and their usage and using them in two languages mainly, English and Uzbek.*

Key words: *clothing, linguistic feature, fashion, casual peaked, tweed caps, floppy hats, thin bands of colour.*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7569494>

Both English and Uzbek languages are rich in vocabulary that we can face up to wide range of vocabulary and their features according to linguistic sphere. It is necessary to analyze linguistic features of the words in any language. Therefore, in this article we are going to show these kinds of features in both compared languages with words related to fashion.

There is an enormous amount of English vocabulary surrounding clothing, and fashion in general, so here we have a run down of some of the terms. Of course, these are all words and phrases that will be useful whenever we are seeking to talk about clothing. More specifically, hats are distinctly in fashion at the moment, and may well feature strongly in Linguistics. Here are some of the more popular types: beany (baggy, woollen hat), cap (a casual peaked hat, sometimes called a baseball cap), flat cap (traditionally worn by older people, these are tweed caps, with a firm peak, which are very fashionable), Panama hat (a white or ivory formal hat, usually worn by men, and very stylish with smart casual wear), floppy hat (any hat with a wide, loose brim). On top of headwear we might come across jewellery. Earrings go, unsurprisingly, in the ears. A necklace, equally predictably, is jewellery that is worn on the neck, usually with a silver or gold chain.

There are two kinds of t-shirts, which are casual, short sleeved tops. A round neck t-shirt has a round neck hole (not really so confusing, this English) and a Polo shirt is slightly more formal, with a collar. A shirt is a long-sleeved garment (although, confusingly, there are short sleeved types), often made of cotton, with buttons up the front. A blouse is a shirt usually worn by women, with a more fitted styles and a smaller collar.

A jumper is the woollen or cotton extra layer that is worn over the shirt, handy for British winters...and Springs, Autumns and, sadly, often summer. It is also known as a jersey or pullover. A jumper with buttons which opens up fully is known as a cardigan, or cardy for

short. A sleeveless jumper is called a tank top. Less formal tops include sweat shirts, a cotton casual pullover, often with a picture or logo on it. A hoodie is like a sweat shirt, but includes a hood. Outer garments for outdoor wear are called coats. But there are many varieties of these: bomber jackets (short coats), golf coats, rain coats, overcoats (heavy, warm and formal coats), Mackintoshes and waterproofs – sometimes called kagoules and carried in case of wet weather – are other common types of coat.

If we observe terms skirts and dresses can cause confusion. A skirt starts at the waist, while a dress is full length. A kilt is a heavy, pleated skirt worn by women and traditionally by Scotsmen, allegedly with nothing underneath, although that is probably not true. A sarong is a loose skirt that is tied at the waist. Usually it is worn by women, but occasionally by men. The footballer David Beckham introduced a trend for men to wear sarongs a few years ago. Sometimes tights (all in one) or stockings (separate for each leg) can be worn under skirts and dresses. There are many styles of shoe; crocks, sandals, brogues, lace ups, trainers, boots, slippers. Under these people often wear socks – very short socks often worn with trainers and shorts are called trainer socks, slightly bigger are ankle socks. In the old days, shorts were worn mostly by men and boys, along with knee length socks. These are called long socks.

There is much vocabulary describing styles – stripes (thin bands of colour); polka dot (summery spots of colour), elegant is a term for smart, and smart casual usually means jacket and trousers, with open necked shirt for men, the term is looser for women. Formal means a suit for men, a dress, blouse and skirt/trousers or trouser suit for women. As with most aspects of using the English language, as we build up our vocabulary around fashion, we can make ourselves better understood.

In conclusion, the linguistics associated with style and fashion are typically ones embedded with signs and symbols that represented a set of values. One only needs think of the Mao jacket or the Cheongsam to see how Chinese fashion is not only associated with the nation but also the values of its culture. The Cheongsam was meant to act as a sign of the shapeliness of the female form but also to conceal any parts of the body whose exposure would be viewed as immodest. Modesty and other values are, therefore, what drive different ôfashionsö and ôstylesö in clothing as surely as Leach reveals that Eco maintains they do in architecture and public structures.

References:

1. Jalolov J.J., Makhkamova G.T., Ashurov Sh.S. English language Teaching Methodology. Tashkent:Fan va texnologiya, 2015.
2. Richards J.C., Rodgers Th.S. Approaches and methods. CUP: On-line Publication, 2010. <http://dx.doi.org/10/1017/CBO9780511667305>
3. <http://blog.tjaylor.net/teaching-methods/>
4. <http://www.slideshare.net/maviscinal/direct-method-5550563?related=1>
- 5 Pham Hoa Hiep. “Imported” Communicative Language Teaching Implications for Local Teaching. // English Teaching Forum Journal. V.43, No4, 2005. p.2-9.